

Anglican Church of Korea

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Entry tags: Protestantism, Korean Religions, Abrahamic, Religious Group, Christianity of the global South

The Anglican Church of Korea is a Christian denomination belonging to the Anglican Communion, the global family of churches with roots in the Church of England. Among the many Christian bodies in South Korea, the Anglican Church ranks among the smaller denominations, though it has experienced steady growth in recent years. The current membership numbers around 65,000 communicants. The Anglican Church is distinctive in incorporating both Roman Catholic and Protestant elements in its theology, organization, and worship. The church is divided into three dioceses, Seoul, Busan, and Daejeon, each headed by a bishop, and the three bishops rotate the national leadership as archbishop. Worship in the Anglican Church is similar to Roman Catholic practice, with ornate clerical vestments and said or chanted prayers. It also has monastic orders of monks and nuns. And yet, like other Anglican bodies, it is officially Protestant. The church does not recognize the authority of the pope and departs from Roman Catholic tradition in other ways, as in the ordination of women. Moreover, the Anglicans are different from both the Roman Catholics and Protestants in Korea in embracing more open and progressive views on such social issues as LGBTQ rights. In the past, church members have been active in the democratic movement, and one of the priorities of the church today is the reunification of the Korean peninsula. The first Anglican missionaries arrived in Incheon in 1890, under the leadership of Bishop Charles John Corfe. In laying down the church's foundation in Korea, they established churches, as well as schools and hospitals throughout the country. The Anglican missionaries and clergy emphasized sensitivity to Korean culture. They built many churches in the traditional Korean style, and two of their bishops, Mark Napier Trollope and Richard Rutt, were pioneering scholars in Korean studies. During the Japanese colonial period (1910-1945), the Anglican Church was unique among Protestant bodies in having both the Koreans and the Japanese, as well as the English, work together with equal rights. In 1923, the church established St. Michael's Theological Institute to train its clergy; it later expanded to become Sungkonghoe University, a major institution of higher learning in South Korea. In 1924, the cathedral Church of St. Mary the Virgin and St. Nicholas, the only example of Romanesque architecture in East Asia, was erected in Seoul. The first native Korean priest, Mark Kim (Kim Huijun), was ordained in 1915, and the first Korean bishop, Cheonhwan Lee, was installed in 1965. From its founding, the Anglican Church in Korea had been under the authority of the Archbishop of Canterbury. Then, in 1993, the church became an independent national church, an autonomous province within the Anglican Communion.

Date Range: 1890 CE - 2021 CE

Region: Korea (1890-2021 CE)

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, South Korea, North Korea

Korean peninsula (including Jeju Island) from the late 19th century to the present day.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Yi Chaejong. *Taehan Songgonghoe paengnyonsa: 1890-1990* [Hundred-year history of the Anglican Church of Korea]. Seoul: Taehan Songgonghoe ch'ulp'anbu, 1990.
- Source 2: Whelan, John B. "The Anglican Church in Korea." *International Review of Missions* 49 (1960): 157-166.
- Source 3: Kim, Sean C. "Via Media in the Land of Morning Calm: The Anglican Church in Korea." *Journal of Korean Religions* 4, no.1 (April 2013): 71-98.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.skh.or.kr>
- Source 1 Description: official website for the Anglican Church of Korea
- Source 2 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20140413000200/http://seoulanglican.com/>
- Source 2 Description: official website of English-speaking ministry at the Anglican cathedral in Seoul

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <http://anglicanhistory.org/asia/kr/>
- Source 1 Description: historical documents on Korean Anglicanism

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Anglican Church of Korea is active in the ecumenical movement, interacting with other Christian groups, as well as with other religious traditions.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Some members are initiated into the community through infant baptism, arranged by their parents.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: There are personal conversions from other Christian denominations and other religious traditions, as well as by those who had no previous religious affiliation.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Baptism is the official ritual through which a newcomer is initiated into the community.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Christian groups, the church emphasizes sharing one's faith and inviting others to worship and other activities.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Members may choose to leave the church or be required to leave for personal or theological reasons, and they would no longer be considered part of the community.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 65000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.08

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Similar to the Roman Catholic Church, the Anglican Church has an official hierarchy of bishops, priests, and deacons. But, generally, the laity have greater participation and more opportunities for leadership.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: As with other Christian groups, the Bible is the main sacred text to Anglicans. There are many different translations in Korean. The one used officially today by the Korean Anglican Church is the Common Translation Bible, also used by the Korean Orthodox Church. While this version is used in the churches, the members may also use other translations in their private study and devotions.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Biblical scholarship at seminaries and universities informs the community, and there is a great deal of latitude in terms of personal interpretation of scripture.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: As with other Christian groups, the Bible is the central text. And like other Anglicans, the Korean Church also uses the Book of Common Prayer for personal and public worship.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the many church buildings throughout the country, the central place of worship and polity is the cathedral Church of St. Mary the Virgin and St. Nicholas in Seoul, the only example of Romanesque architecture in East Asia.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the Western-style church buildings, the Anglicans have also built churches using traditional Korean architecture (hanok), the most well-known one being Ganghwa Anglican Church,

built in 1900.

↳ Tombs:
– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:
– Yes

↳ Temples:
– No

↳ Altars:
– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:
– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
– Yes [specify]: monasteries, convents, shrines

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:
– On persons
– At home
– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:
– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Stained glass windows with images from scripture and church history adorn many churches.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: The churches are the primary space for worship.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: In many churches, the altar is traditionally placed on the east side to symbolize praying

toward Jerusalem, the holy city.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Some members will go on pilgrimage to the Holy Land or to England.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Anglicans, like other Christians, believe in the immortality of the soul. The soul survives the body at death to enter the afterlife. The human being is conceived in terms of heart (the seat of emotions), soul/spirit, and body.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Because the Bible is unclear on the afterlife, a number of different beliefs exist in Anglicanism, as they do in Christianity in general. Most subscribe to the belief in heaven for the souls of believers and hell for those of unbelievers. Some Anglicans who lean toward more Roman Catholic views believe in purgatory. There are also some who emphasize bodily resurrection, believing that at Christ's Second Coming, the dead will rise from a state of sleep and be resurrected with transformed bodies to live on a new earth.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: In addition to the concept of heaven and hell, many Anglicans believe there will be resurrection of the body on a new earth when Jesus comes again.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Like most Koreans today, the majority of Anglicans choose cremation over burial of the body. In either case, the body is cleaned and either clothed in traditional burial clothes or formal Western-style clothing such as a suit for a man or dress for a woman.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Christian groups, Anglicans believe in one God, who created the world and interacts with the lives of human beings, and many also believe in angels and demons.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Christians, Anglicans believe in one God, and most subscribe to the belief in the doctrine of the Trinity, which conceives of God as three persons in one: Father, Son, and Holy Spirit. The Father is God the creator of the world, omnipotent, omniscient, and omnipresent. The Son is the incarnation of God in Jesus Christ. The Holy Spirit is the spirit of God that came to believers after the ascension of Jesus to heaven after his resurrection from death. The Trinitarian formula is present in the official worship and prayers.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: omnipotence, omniscience, omnipresence

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: omniscience

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Jesus is believed to be the human incarnation of God.

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Many Anglicans, like their Roman Catholic counterparts, venerate the saints. In particular, prayers to the Virgin Mary are prominent.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Some Anglicans venerate Mary and other saints, former human beings who will hear and answer prayers.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: miracles, signs

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Some Anglicans, like other Christians, believe in the existence of angels as well as demons. But others, of a more rational and liberal bent, would deny their existence, or at least as having any influence in the world.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Some Anglicans believe they have had visions of angels or believe in demonic possession.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Some Anglicans believe in guardian angels who protect them from harm.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Some Anglicans believe in demonic possession, for which an exorcism is required. The church does have an official rite of exorcism, though it is rarely used.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: According to orthodox Christian belief, which forms the basis of Anglican theology, Jesus, the incarnation of God, is both fully human and fully divine, not a mix of human and

divine parts.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: According to the Bible, there is a hierarchy of angels. At the top are the archangels, such as Michael and Raphael. And then there are the seraphim and cherubim, and the rest of the angelic host. As for the forces of evil, Satan or the Devil is the leader of the demons and evil spirits.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: For those Anglicans who lean toward Roman Catholicism, they believe that different saints have different powers. Hence, there are patron saints of various places and groups, as well as for specific functions, such as healing.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

- ↳ Food:
 - No
- ↳ Sacred space(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Sacred object(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: prohibition of worship of other gods
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Yes [specify]: There is debate in the Anglican Communion concerning LGBTQ rights.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Those who believe in angels and demons believe they interact with human beings to bring both benefit and harm.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: For most Christians, the traditional conception of punishment in the afterlife is hell, suffering eternal torment separated from God. Some Anglicans, together with Roman Catholics, believe in purgatory as an intermediate stage between hell and heaven, where the soul is punished for the sins committed in life but will eventually be purified for entrance into heaven. The length of time spent in purgatory depends on the number and severity of the sins.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious

group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: angels and demons

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Anglicanism, like the rest of Christianity, is a religion of salvation.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Together with other Christians, Anglicans believe that Jesus Christ is the Messiah who has come and will come again. Called the Second Coming, the return of Jesus to this world is conceived as an apocalyptic end to this world after a period of tribulation, and the establishment of a new creation, in which Christ will reign forever, bringing an end to evil and suffering. This vision is based on apocalyptic texts in the Bible, in particular the Book of Revelation.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The Second Coming of Jesus will mark the end of time and the beginning of God's reign in a new heaven and earth.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Jesus is the incarnation of God on earth.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: The Second Coming of Jesus signals the end of this world and the beginning of a new world.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Yes [specify]: Anglicans, together with most other Christians, believe that they do not know when Jesus will come again. It could be soon or sometime in the distant future.

Notes: Some Anglicans, of a more conservative bent, may believe in the predictions of Christians who claim to know the details of the Second Coming based on their interpretation of the Bible, in particular the Book of Revelation.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

Notes: Christian values, as preached and lived by Jesus, are seen as at odds with those of the world (e.g., humility vs. pride, poverty vs. wealth).

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Notes: There are many different forms of Anglican/Christian ethics, but in general the main metaphysical/theological basis rests on such moral attributes of God as good, loving, just, and merciful. The believers are called to embody the same attributes in their lives. Two key pillars in Christian ethics are the Ten Commandments, which Christians share with the Jews, and the Sermon on the Mount, in which Jesus lays out his moral vision.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Christian ethics are based on the moral teachings of Jesus.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
 - All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The ultimate model for the moral life for Anglicans, as with other Christians, is Jesus. He is believed to be the embodiment of all the moral attributes to which the faithful strive. And the supreme moral attribute is self-denying love for God and for one another.

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - Yes

- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes

- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes

- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes

- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes

- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - No

- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Anglican Church is led by ordained priests, and the rituals are prescribed by a prayer book.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Anglican Church is led by ordained priests, and the rituals are prescribed by a prayer book.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Congregational worship on Sundays is the primary ritual.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Anglicans address the priest as "Father," and identify themselves as brothers and sisters under God the Father.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: Anglicanism, together with other religions, has been suppressed in North Korea since the division of the country following World War II. Prior to that time, the Anglican Church had a vibrant presence, especially in the Pyongyang. During the Korean War, many Anglicans, both clergy and laity, were martyred by the communists. Officially, the Anglican Church of Korea includes both North and South Korea, but there is no evidence of practicing Anglicans in the former.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Because of its focus on reunification, the Anglican Church of Korea has helped address the famines in North Korea, sending relief through its own agencies as well as in partnership with other church and NGO groups.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: South Korea has not experienced famine in recent years, but during the Korean War and in the years following the conflict, Anglicans as well as Koreans in general received aid and relief from the United States and other countries through church groups and non-governmental organizations.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Poverty relief is provided through various institutional channels. Individual parishes may have committees that focus on outreach to the poor and mobilize resources and labor within the church. Anglicans also have access to national and international relief agencies affiliated with the denomination as well as other Christian groups.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Many other religious groups as well as non-governmental organizations provide poverty relief in South Korea.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: The church runs homes for the elderly and infirm throughout the country.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: South Korea has many options of the care of the elderly and the infirm, run by both churches and the private sector.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Sungkonghoe University provides higher education to Anglicans as well as the general Korean population, and it has a graduate program for those desiring ordination in the church.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Anglicans can attend the Sungkonghoe University, as well as any other institutions of higher learning in South Korea.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Anglican bodies, the church in Korea is organized according to dioceses, a specified region headed by a bishop. All the churches within a diocese lie under the direction of the bishop. And each church is headed by a priest and a group of lay leaders called the Vestry. In the case of Korea, there are three dioceses, each anchored in a major city, Seoul, Busan, and Daejeon. The three bishops rotate the national leadership as archbishop. And the three diocese form what is known as a province in the Anglican Communion, roughly corresponding to a country but in some cases involving more than one country. The Anglican Communion is the global family of churches that share history, theology, and worship with the Church of England, and its headquarters are in London. But the Church of England has no jurisdictional authority over the other churches in the Communion. Hence, the leader of the Church in England, the Archbishop of Canterbury, does not have the power to mandate doctrine and practice in the way that the pope can in the Roman Catholic Church.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Anglican Church of Korea has historically been very active in the ecumenical movement, working for unity with other Christian groups.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Anglican Church has a calendar of commemorating saints and other feast days.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)